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DEVELOPMENT OF ONLINE LEARNING PRACTICES IN A JAPANESE UNIVERSITY BASED ON THE QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEYS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to clarify the development of online learning practice of engineering education in a Japanese university under the pandemic of the COVID-19. The research question is how online learning, especially blended learning, was practiced. By 2020, advances in Internet technology and its widespread use had already formed the basis for online classes. However, face-to-face classes were the mainstream, and there were few online classes for undergraduate education. We will present the development of online learning at a Japanese university, which is a private technical university in the bay area of Tokyo, Japan, as an example. This university had conducted all classes online in the first semester of 2020. The transition to online classes was unexpected, and classes started in May, a month late. In the second semester, some classes were face-to-face, while many classes were online. We will present:

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1. how progressed the teaching style to blended learning,
2. how changed the students' understanding of classes,
3. how changed the students' satisfaction level of classes.

The significant difference is that blended learning started in the second semester. The understanding and satisfaction of the students have improved in the second semester. The background of this development is also that the faculty, administrators, and students collaborated to work on education innovation.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are two challenges facing engineering education today. One is the promotion of digitalization toward the pandemic of COVID-19. Universities around the world are currently taking various steps toward the digitization of higher education. According to a study by Crawford et al., higher education institutions worldwide respond that some universities have no response at all, while others have a strategy of closing campuses and redeveloping a complete online curriculum [1]. The other is integration with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and emerging technologies and employability and lifelong learning. Editor of the European Journal of Engineering Education says, "With all the challenges lining up, engineering education in 2030 will require a student-centered and flexible curriculum, personalized learning environments and transformation of learning experiences into students' competences. [2]" The two issues are interconnected. The case of a German university reports that COVID-19 promotes the digitization of university education [3]. A study by the British Computer Science Education Community reports that COVID-19 has a significant impact not only negative but also positive on all stages of education [4]. In the United States, the Chronicle of Higher Education surveyed faculty members and academic administrators. Half of the faculty members do not have sufficient experience in online learning, then training on online learning is emphasized [5]. In engineering education, a survey of university faculty and students conducted at a state university in Long Beach, California, reports on the challenges of university education in the COVID-19 disaster [6]. The COVID-19 has also provided an opportunity for universities to innovate.

Regarding Japan, Kang reports in detail on higher education as of the spring of 2020 based on the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) surveys [7]. In Japan, the semester begins on April 1st. However, according to a survey by the MEXT, 86.9% of universities and colleges postponed the start. Furthermore, although the semester started about a month later, 90.0% of the universities and colleges had only distance classes. Although distance learning started relatively smoothly in response to a sudden situation, the quality of education was questioned by students and the MEXT. A Japanese university began a survey on distance learning in June 2020. Details will be described in the next section. The results of the June survey were reported at the IEEE International Conference on Teaching, Assessment, and Learning for Engineering (IEEE TALE) [8]. In addition, faculty members and administrators held a workshop meeting on online learning on

campus periodically. It was also an opportunity for professional development who need the skills of online learning . MEXT introduced the efforts of this university to improve the quality of teaching using online as an excellent example [9]. In engineering education at a graduate school in Spain, they report that the shift from face-to-face to blended and full-online learning has improved the number of enrollments, students' satisfaction, and academic performance [10]. In this presentation, we will report on the practice at a Japanese university in Japan.

2 METHODOLOGY

As shown in Table 1, this university conducted five "Surveys on Distance Learning" in 2020 academic year. These surveys were anonymous questionnaire surveys using a website. The first survey was conducted on faculty members from June 10 to 20 of the first semester, one month after classes. We received responses from 466 faculty members (78.1% response rate). The second survey was conducted on faculty members from August 19 to 31 after the first semester ended, and 390 faculty members responded (60.9% response rate). The third survey was conducted on students from August 27 to September 3. Responses were received from 3,616 students (40.1% response rate). The fourth survey was conducted from February 12 to 19 after the end of the second semester. 310 faculty members responded (48.4% response rate). The fifth survey was conducted on students from February 16 to March 2. Responses were received from 4,416 students (49.0% response rate). Faculty members include part-time lecturers. Students include full-time undergraduate and graduate students. We prepared both Japanese and English versions of the questionnaires.

Table 1. Questionnaire survey on distance learning in 2020 academic year

Web survey	Survey target	Survey period	Number of respondents (response rate)
First semester June	Faculty member (inc. part-time)	June 10-20, 2020	468 (78.1%)
First semester Aug.	Faculty member (inc. part-time)	Aug. 19-31 , 2020	390 (60.9%)
	Student (Inc. graduate students)	Aug. 27-Sept. 3, 2020	3,616(40.1%)
Second semester	Faculty member (inc. part-time)	Feb. 12-19, 2021	310(48.4%)
	Student (Inc. graduate students)	Feb. 16-Mar. 2, 2021	4,416(49.0%)

3 RESULTS

The following three points show the development of online learning. First is the progress of the teaching style. The first survey focused on only conducting online teaching. After that, the horizons expanded to flipped classrooms and blended learning. The next is the students' understanding and satisfaction with the classes. Did the introduction of flipped classrooms and blended learning improve the understanding and satisfaction of the classes?

3.1 Progress of teaching style

The development of online learning practice in this university is reflected in the progress of teaching style. We asked faculty members about the teaching style each time they surveyed. Question options were updated with each survey, receiving feedback from the progress of distance learning. As shown in Figure 1., in the first semester June survey, there were three options for the teaching style, and we asked multiple answers. 90% of university faculty members are live. In the first semester August survey, there were four options. Practices such as flipped classroom that combine on-demand and live have been added. Then, the faculty members selected one main teaching style for each of the lectures, seminars, and experiments, practical training. The live type accounts for the majority, and is the most common. However, flipped classroom are practiced in 12% of lectures, 13% of seminars, and 20% of experiments, practical training. Classes only on demand are few in lectures (11%), seminars (4%), and experiments, practical training (11%). In the second semester survey, there were five options. Blended learning, which combines face-to-face and online learning, has been added. Although it is as low as 6% in lectures, it accounts for 31% of seminars and 44% of experiments, practical training.

Fig. 1-1. Main teaching style (first semester June, faculty members survey)

Fig. 1-2. Main teaching style of lectures (first semester Aug. and second semester)

Fig. 1-4. Main teaching style of experiments and practical training (first semester Aug. and second semester)

Fig. 1-3. Main teaching style of seminars (first semester Aug. and second semester)

graph legends of Fig. 1-2, 1-3, 1-4

- 1. On-demand (asynchronous) material distribution type
- 2. On-demand (asynchronous) video / audio distribution type
- 3. Live (simultaneous interactive) type
- 4. Combine live (simultaneous interactive) and on-demand: flipped classroom, etc.
- 5. Combine face-to-face and live (simultaneous interactive): blended learning, etc.

3.2 Students' understanding of the class

The development of online learning practice in this university is reflected in students' understanding of the class. From the first semester to the second semester, students' understanding of the class increased. This is most evident in seminars. The change in the percentage of "Very good" as indicated by the red circle in Fig.2 shows students' understanding of the class. The percentage of "Very good" increased by 6 points for lectures, 11 points for seminars, and 4 points for experiments, practical training. And the percentage of "Bad" and "Not good" decreased.

3.3 Students' satisfaction of the class

The development of online learning practices in this university is also reflected in the students' satisfaction of the class. From the first semester to the second semester, students' satisfaction increased. This is most evident in seminars. The change in the percentage of "Very satisfied" classes as indicated by the red circle in Fig. 3 shows the increase of students' satisfaction of the class. The percentage of "Very satisfied"

increased by 6 points for lectures, 10 points for seminars, and 2 points for experiments, practical training. And the percentages of "Very dissatisfied" and "Dissatisfied" decreased.

Fig. 2. Students' understanding of the class (first semester Aug. and second semester)

Fig. 3. Students' satisfaction of the class (first semester Aug. and second semester)

4 DISCUSSION

The pandemic of COVID-19 has brought the university an unexpected response to the implementation of full distance learning. It is also related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and emerging technologies, employability and lifelong learning. Editor of the European Journal of Engineering Education said, "With all the challenges lining up, engineering education in 2030 will require a student-centered and flexible curriculum, personalized learning environments and transformation of learning experiences into students' competences. [2] "

In this study, we reported on the progress of teaching style from a large-scale questionnaire survey conducted to faculty members and students at a private technical university in Tokyo bay area, Japan. The teaching style has expanded from only online teaching to flipped classrooms and blended learning. Students' understanding the class and satisfaction of the class both improved in the second semester after introducing blended learning. The effect was particularly obvious to the seminars. In this university, faculty members and administrators held a workshop meeting on online teaching periodically. These organizational efforts may be reflected in the background of the development of online learning in this university. Further progress is desired toward the realization of engineering education in 2030.

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